

ISic0246

I.Sicily inscription 0246

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]ar[---]

2. [---b]en(e) · merent[---]

3. [---] vixi(t) · an(nis) · LXXX

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285289

EDR 127512

EDCS 10900671

Bibliography

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese.

Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica. Palermo / Rome. At 173
undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 92b

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0246. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4334713>